

Supervisor: Dr Jennifer Kieran

Authors: James Lalor O'Neill, Victoria Lien, Bozena Skehan, Mary Coleman, Sarah Wrigley

What is the evidence for the use of synthetic growth factors (erythropoietin and GCSF) to support Hepatitis C treatment?

Hepatitis C (HCV) is an RNA virus which causes hepatocellular damage leading to cirrhosis, hepatocellular cancer, liver failure and death, if left untreated. The number of chronically infected persons worldwide is estimated at over 200 million.¹ Host factors such as age, gender and alcohol, and viral factors such as genotype, mode of transmission and viral load affect prognosis and response to treatment.² The aim of treatment is to achieve a sustained virological response (SVR), which is defined as undetectable HCV RNA six months after the end of therapy.³ This leads to permanent eradication of the virus in 98.3% of patients.⁴ Treatment has been based upon interferon and ribavirin since the 1990s.³ Interferons are naturally occurring proteins that support immune response to viruses and directly inhibit viral replication. Ribavirin is a ribonucleoside analogue that acts by incorporation into viral RNA, inducing point mutations in the viral genome. The combination of interferon or pegylated interferon (1.5 µg/kg/week) and repairing (800-1200mg/day) achieves SVR in 54-56% of patients.⁵ Newer drugs such as telaprevir and boceprevir, potent inhibitors of the NS3/4A serine protease required for RNA replication, have shown SVR in 65% of previous non-responders.^{6,7} All current HCV drugs are associated with the development of side-effects, notably anaemia and neutropenia. These haematological abnormalities have been shown to cause dose reductions and discontinuation of therapy in up to 25% and 3% of patients, treated with PegINF and ribavirin, respectively.⁸ Sub-optimal dosing or ceasing of treatment may decrease the rate of SVR in patients infected with

genotype1 HCV.⁹ The management of these side effects, either by reducing therapy or by direct treatment with erythropoietin (EPO) and gCSF, is an issue causing some contention.

The risk of developing anaemia increases proportionally with ribavirin dose, with one study showing increased anaemia (6-16%) following a dose increase from 12-16mg/kg.¹⁰ The package insert for ribavirin recommends a dose reduction if Hb levels fall below 10g/dL, and discontinuation at less than 8.5g/dL. This is a particular problem in relation to HCV genotype 1, the SVR for which is particularly dose dependent, with higher doses resulting in a better SVR in comparison to genotypes 2 and 3.¹⁰ Hadziyannis and colleagues provide further evidence that dose reductions of ribavirin can cause lower SVR rates in patients with HCV genotype1.¹¹

In light of this, the use of erythropoietin (EPO) is being considered as an alternative means of managing HCV therapy-induced anaemia, to avoid dose reductions. Numerous studies have shown that administering weekly doses of 40,000 IU of EPO improves ribavirin-induced anaemia and thus quality of life, and allows adherence to full-dose ribavirin.¹² Although no direct relationship between EPO and SVR rates has been established, it allows toleration of higher doses of ribavirin which, in turn, increases SVR rates and decreases relapse rates.¹³

Leukopenia is associated with bone marrow suppression in HCV infected individuals resulting from treatment with the glycoprotein Pegylated-Interferon. Pegylated Interferon therapy can be initiated using the alpha-2a type, or alpha-2b type, with higher incidences of bone marrow suppression associated with the alpha-2a type.¹⁴ As a result, neutropenia is the most common cause of its dose reduction or discontinuation.^{5,15} The package insert of PegIFN recommends dose reduction for patients with a neutrophil count less than 750 cells/mm³, and discontinuation if the neutrophil count falls below 500 cells/mm³. However, lowering doses of Peg-IFN may also lower SVR rates by up to 13% in genotype1 patients.⁵

The use of GCSF (300µg twice a week) as an alternative strategy to Peg-IFN dose reduction is being considered to manage neutropenia. Studies by Van Thiel and Koskinas have shown that GCSF increases neutrophil counts, improves drug adherence and minimises dose reduction, but in both cases the effect on SVR rates was statistically insignificant.^{16,17}

While studies have shown that EPO and GCSF are effective in improving the haematological side-effects of HCV therapy, thereby improving quality of life and limiting dose reduction, it is still unclear whether maintaining higher doses of HCV therapy with expensive growth factors to improve SVR rates in genotype1 patients is cost-effective. Cost-effectiveness is sensitive to the effect of dose reduction on SVR rates.¹⁸ Given the cost of EPO and GCSF, it may be necessary to refine indications for their use by identifying the subset of patients more prone to experience haematological toxicity during therapy. Risk factors for the development of anaemia include; sex (F>M), increasing age, baseline ALT, pre-existing cirrhosis and lower baseline.^{19,20} Additionally, the relationship between ribavirin dose reduction and SVR rates has only been seen in genotype1 patients. Because genotype1 patients are more likely to experience haemolytic anaemia, the Swiss Association for the Study of the Liver (SASL) concluded that EPO use is only indicated for these patients.²¹ Similarly, risk factors exist for the development of neutropenia. In a study in which 142 HCV-infected patients received peginterferon-alpha2a plus ribavirin, a baseline neutrophil count below 2050/mm(3) (HR: 3.59; 95% CI: 1.77-7.28) and baseline weight <60 kg (HR: 2.21; 95% CI: 1.04-4.56) were independently associated with the development of neutropenia.²² Predicting the likelihood of adverse effects based on proven risk factors would positively influence cost effectiveness of administering artificial growth factors.

Recently, telaprevir and boceprevir, effective in the treatment of treatment-experienced patients and other HCV genotypes, have also been shown to increase the incidence of anaemia from 17% to 27%, with 4% having severe anaemia (Hb<8.5g/dl).²³ Thus, the demand for EPO to increase tolerability of HCV therapy may increase.

In conclusion, the treatment of Hepatitis C remains a difficult task as it is extremely hard to find the balance between the efficient dose of the drugs and their side effects. Until new antiviral drugs with a reduced side effect profile are found, interferon and ribavirin utilization must be optimized. Thanks to EPO and GCSF, the long-term treatment plan of HCV therapy may more sustainable.

Despite their effectiveness in improving the haematological side-effects of HCV therapy, more research is needed to establish a clearer relationship between the use of haematological growth

factors and SVR rates. In addition, because certain factors predispose to haematological toxicity, use of synthetic growth factors can be made more cost-efficient by targeting at risk patients.

References:

1. EASL Clinical Practice Guidelines: Management of hepatitis C virus infection European Association for the Study of the Liver 1 (YEAR)
2. Sievert M, Management issues in chronic viral hepatitis: Hepatitis C *J Gastroen Hepatol* (2002) 17, 415–422
3. Brau N, Epetin alfa treatment for acute anaemia during interferon plus ribavirin combination therapy for chronic hepatitis C. *Journal of Viral Hepatitis* 2004; 11: 191-197.
4. McHutchison JG, Davis GL, Esteban-Mur R Durability of sustained viral response in patients with chronic hepatitis C after treatment with interferon alfa-2b alone or in combination with ribavirin [Abstract]. *Hepatology* 2001; 34(4 part 2)
5. Manns MP, McHutchison JG, Gordon SC Peginterferon alfa-2b plus ribavirin compared with interferon alfa-2b plus ribavirin for initial treatment of chronic hepatitis C: a randomised trial. *Lancet* 2001; 358(9286) 958-965.
6. Crotty S, Maag D, Arnold JJ The broad spectrum antiviral ribonucleoside ribavirin is an RNA virus mutagen. *Nat. Med.* 2000;6 :1375-9
7. Fontainea H, Pola S, Antiviral activity of telaprevir and boceprevir for the treatment of hepatitis C virus infection in treatment- experienced patients *Clinics and Research in Hepatology and Gastroenterology* (2011) 35, S59—S63
8. Fried MW. Side effects of therapy of hepatitis C and their management. *Hepatology* 2002; 36 (suppl.1): S237-S244.
9. McHutchison JG, Manns M, Patel K, et al. Adherence to combination therapy enhances sustained response in genotype1- infected patients with chronic hepatitis C. *Gastroenterology* 2002; 123: 1061-1069

10. Snoek E, Wade JR, Duff F, Lamb M, Jorga K Predicting sustained virological response and anaemia in chronic hepatitis C patients treated with peginterferon alfa-2a (40KD) plus ribavirin. *Br J Clin Pharmacol*. 2006 Dec;62(6):699-709
11. Hadziyannis SJ, Morgan T, Balan V, et al. Peginterferon alfa-2a (40 kilodaltons) and ribavirin combination therapy in chronic hepatitis C: randomised study of effect of treatment duration and ribavirin dose. *Ann Intern Med*
12. Dieterich DT, Wasserman R, Brau N et al. Once-weekly epoetin alfa improves anaemia and facilitates maintenance ribavirin dosing in hepatitis C virus-infected patients receiving ribavirin plus interferon alfa. *Am J Gastroenterology* 2003; 98(11): 2491-2499.
13. Shiffman ML, Salvatore J, Hubbard S et al. Treatment of chronic hepatitis C virus genotype 1 with peginterferon, ribavirin and epoetin alpha. *Hepatology* 2007; 46: 371-379.
14. Mira JA, Lope-Cortes LF, Merino D, Arizcorreta-Yarza A, Rivero A, Collado A, Ríos-Villegas MJ, González-Serrano M, Torres-Tortoso M, Macías J, Valera-Bestard B, Fernández-Fuertes E, Girón-González JA, Lozano F, Pineda JA , Predictors of severe haematological toxicity secondary to pegylated interferon plus ribavirin treatment in HIV-HCV-coinfected patients *Anti Vir Therapy* 2007;12(8):1225-35.
15. Fried MW, Shiffman ML, Reddy KR, et al. Peginterferon alfa-2a plus ribavirin for chronic hepatitis C virus infection. *N Eng J Med* 2002; 36 (5 suppl. 1): S3-S15
16. Van Thiel DH, Faruki H, Friedlander L, et al. Combination treatment of advanced HCV associated liver disease with interferon and GCSF. *Hepatogastroenterology* 1995; 42: 907-912
17. Koskinas J, Zacharakis G, Sideropoulos J et al. Granulocyte Colony Stimulating Factor in HCV genotype-1 patients who develop Peg-IFN- α 2b related severe neutropenia: A preliminary report on treatment, safety and efficacy. *J Med Virol* 2009; 81: 848-852.
18. Chapko MK, Dominitz JA. Cost effectiveness of growth factors during hepatitis C anti-viral therapy. *Aliment Pharmacol Ther* 2006, 24: 1067-1077.
19. Snoeck E, Wade JR, Duff F, Lamb M, Jorga K. Predicting sustained virological response and anaemia in chronic hepatitis C patients treated with peginterferon alfa-2a (40KD) plus ribavirin. *Br J Clin Pharmacol*. 2006 Dec;62(6):699-709.
20. Snoeck E, Wade JR, Duff F, Lamb M, Jorga K. Predicting sustained virological response and anaemia in chronic hepatitis C patients treated with peginterferon alfa-2a (40KD) plus ribavirin. *Br J Clin Pharmacol*. 2006 Dec;62(6):699-709.
21. Stickel F, Helbing B, Heim M et al. Critical review of the use of erythropoietin in the treatment of anaemia during therapy for chronic hepatitis C. *Journal of Viral Hepatitis* 2012; 19, 77-87.

22. Fuster D, Huertas JA, Gomez G, Solà R, González García J, Vilaró J, Pedrol E, Force L, Tor J, Sirera G, Videla S, Planas R, Clotet B, Tural C; PEG-TOX Research Group. Short communication. Baseline factors associated with haematological toxicity that leads to a dosage reduction of pegylated interferon-alpha2a and ribavirin in HIV- and HCV-coinfected patients on HCV antiviral therapy. *Antivir Ther.* 2005;10(7):841-7.

23. Pawlotsky JM. The results of phase III trials with telaprevir and boceprevir presented at the Liver Meeting2010: a new standard of care for hepatitis C virus genotype 1 infection, but with issues still pending. *Gastroenterology* 2011; 140: 746–760